

LANGUAGE FEELING

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17618944>

Siddikjon Muminov,

Professor of FerSU,

Doctor of Philological Sciences

siddiqjon.muminov@bk.ru

ANNOTATION: *The article analyzes the process of giving the Uzbek language the status of a state language, obstacles and difficulties on this path, the development of a sense of language in the hearts is the best way to raise the prestige of the Uzbek language as a state language.*

KEYWORDS AND EXPRESSIONS: *language, state language, state language status, developing.*

"The adoption in Uzbekistan on October 21, 1989, of the law on the state language, which our people have dreamed of, aspired to, and fought for for centuries, was the first bold step towards the country's sovereignty and independence" [1,1]. I did not quote this sentence in vain from the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Radically Enhance the Role and Authority of the Uzbek Language as the State Language." Because beneath every sentence, every word in this historical Decree lie a world of meanings, a chain of history, which must be read repeatedly, without rushing, with a deep feeling. Note: "the law on the state language, which our people have dreamed, strived for, and fought for for centuries..." Yes, this law was not just a law. The essence of this law is deeply understood by people who are at least fifty years old and consider themselves

true sons and daughters of this country. Because they saw with their own eyes the trampling of our national language, along with our national values and traditions, they struggled and suffered, unable to speak their native language at home, manage paperwork, and engage in scientific and artistic creativity. Finally, in 1988, the "Draft Law on Languages of the Uzbek SSR" was submitted for public discussion. Notice: the "Draft Law on Languages (!) " is not a "Draft Law on Granting State Language Status to the Uzbek Language (!) "!" In my personal archive, there are numerous articles expressing the opinions of various specialists, our compatriots of different ages and genders who participated in the discussion of this bill: "Multilingualism - an international virtue" ("Young Leninist," April 15, 1989); "Let's Be Bilingual" ("Young Leninist," January 5, 1989); "My Firm Opinion" ("Fergana

Pravda," July 4, 1989)... As can be seen from the titles, such articles mainly advocated multilingualism and bilingualism, or completely opposed granting Uzbek the status of state language. However, thanks to the courageous struggle and bravery of the fearless and selfless sons of our people, a law was signed granting the Uzbek language the status of the state language. This, as emphasized in the Presidential Decree, "was the first bold step towards the country's sovereignty and independence." After the first bold step, significant changes were noticeable in the language sphere: Uzbek language courses were opened in organizations, and leaders who did not know or did not know Uzbek well began to study the language, albeit voluntarily and compulsorily. However, within a year or two, language policy began to lose its relevance. Deeply angered by this, selfless intellectuals began to cry out in the press again: Mashrab Boboyev. "When will you become a people..." // "Literature and Art of Uzbekistan," December 7, 1990; Yoldosh Solijonov. "I will tell you what I have to say..." // "Fergana tongi," November 7, 1991; A. Ibodinov, A. Abdullayev. "For show again?" // "Kommuna," August 28, 1991; H. Rustamov. "What other assignment are you waiting for?" // "Fergana Truth," October 11, 1993.

Despite the efforts of scholars, writers, and journalists, instances of non-compliance with and disregard for the articles of the state language law

continued. As a result, on December 21, 1995, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments and Additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Language" in a new edition was published.

This law, in its new edition, issued to improve the process of consistent implementation of the state language and ensure the perfect transition to the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script, consists of twenty-four articles, and it cannot be said that everyone approached and followed all its articles with the same responsibility as before. In particular, despite the fact that Article 20 of the law clearly states that "Textboards, announcements, price lists, and other texts of visual and oral information are formalized and published in the state language," on the signboards of enterprises and institutions, such words as "AGAMA," "GRANT," "ELEGANT," "EZIDIYOR," "MIR KOVROV," characteristic of the European or Arabic language, such as "AL-MUBIN," "AL-BARAKA," imitation of the Turkish language, such as "MODALAR EVI," are used; writing Russian advertisements and announcements inherited from the former Soviet Union ("OTKRITO," "ZAKRITO," "MI OTKRILIS," "SKORO OTKROYEMSYA," "SROCHNOYE FOTO" and others); In mutual conversations, they continued speaking words like "PAPASHKA, MAMASHKA," "ZAVTRAK," "OBED," "UJIN," "POCHTI," "CENTER," "OSTANOVKA," addressing friends and

companions as DILYA, GULYA, ZULYA, TOLIK, ALIK, GENA, contaminating their mother tongue. The "battle" in the mass media against those who treated the state language, which was won at the cost of many struggles, with such disrespect did not stop: [2,3,4]; O. Nasriddinova. Where is this "Alisher"? // "Fergana Truth," April 5, 2014; Siddiq Mo'min. "Our language is pure, but what about our speech?" // "Ma'naviyat," 2008, October; Turgun Azizov. "Literary language - the main criterion" // "Literature and Art of Uzbekistan," October 18, 2013; Zebo Kutliyeva. "His tongue has returned'..." // "Hurriyat," October 22, 2019...

In the informational letter of the international scientific-practical conference "Current Issues of Teaching the State Language: Problems and Solutions," which is planned to be held in cooperation with the Fergana regional administration and the Faculty of Philology of Fergana State University, which is the reason for writing this article, it is noted that the main goal of the conference is "to determine the next main tasks to increase the prestige and status of the Uzbek language..., to exchange views on issues of speech culture, to analyze the work done in the field and to develop proposals for further improvement." Accordingly, at the beginning of our article, we attempted to analyze, at least partially, the relevance of the problem being covered, the work done and being done in the field. Now we

will try to provide conclusions and recommendations on the topic.

In the years when the winds of freedom were blowing and many secrets of historical truth began to be revealed in the press, excerpts from the report of the Governor-General to the White Tsar during the period of Tsarist Russia were published in the press of our republic: "Your Excellency, we deprived the peoples of Central Asia of their language, deprived them of their religion, burned their books, destroyed their mosques... Now it will take at least two hundred years for them to come to their senses... (!). You see what the Tsarist Russian officials intended to turn the local people into colonies in every way! In a certain sense, they achieved their vile intentions. That is, they managed to dim and extinguish the most noble feelings from the hearts of the local population: love for homeland, faith, language, and religion. Now we have the opportunity to draw a concise conclusion to what we have written above and determine our future work in this area:

a) Despite the fact that the Uzbek language has been granted the status of the state language, Presidential Decrees and Resolutions are being issued on measures to radically increase the prestige and status of the Uzbek language as the state language, and specialists are constantly engaging in various forms of struggle through the mass media, the main reason for the imperfection of our work in this area is the weakening of the sense of language in our hearts;

b) The only way to enhance the prestige and status of the Uzbek language as the state language is to cultivate a lingering sense of language in our hearts, just as it is necessary to heal the inside of a wound, not the surface. For this, it is necessary to strictly implement the Presidential Decrees and Resolutions, not to reduce, but to increase the number of native language and literature lessons in schools, to pay the main attention to instilling in the hearts of our children, from infancy, from childhood, words that awaken a sense of love, loyalty, faith, giving pleasure - to develop a sense of language;

c) we should think about language culture, speech skills, pronunciation rules not only during holidays, but always, every day, every minute, constantly enriching and improving our knowledge in this regard [4,3];

g) no matter how much work is done by agencies, if we ourselves, each of us, do not feel a deep sense of responsibility and do not act individually, one day we will not be able to ask each other:..."where were you?!" [3,3];

d) A nation that cannot make its language great cannot make itself great. The burden of this journey lies with all of us [2,8].

REFERENCES:

1. Мирзиёев Ш. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг Фармони. Ўзбек тилининг давлат тили сифатидаги нуфузи ва мавқеини тубдан ошириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида // HURRIYAT, 2019- yil 22- oktabr.
2. Аъзам А. Тил қайғуси // XXI asr, 2019- yil 10- yanvar.
3. Бобоев М. “Қачон халқ бўласан...” // Ўзбекистон адабиёти ва санъати, 1990 йил 7 декабрь.
4. Мелибоев А. Ҳуштакни ким чалади? // Миллий тикланиш, 2005- yil 28-oktabr.